

Fault-Tolerant Data Aggregation for Reliable Wireless Sensor Networks

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Abstract—precise data & information is the lifeblood for the operation of Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs). Incorrect (faulty data) information may lead to the wrong decision; it decreases the reliability in communication and overall operation of WSN. Fault tolerance is one of the issues in WSNs. Proposed fault-tolerant data aggregation scheme for identifying the faulty data sent by the sensors to the cluster head, where the aggregation is performed. Faulty information or data is discarded before aggregation. It would help to improve the accuracy of data aggregation. Consequently, the transmission overhead reduces, since erroneous data is eliminated. The proposed solution gives better performance by detecting and eliminating faulty data providing nodes

Keywords— WSN; Cluster Head (CH); Error detection; Sink; Fault-Tolerance; Sensor.

I. INTRODUCTION

In any normal system, Fault Tolerance (FT) is responsible for instant identification fault, repair and replacement of faulty components to keep the system functional. Whereas in WSN, fault tolerance is the capability of the WSN to confront the abrupt modifications of network environment such as network bottlenecking, hardware and software faults may lead to failure of a WSN node or the complete network. In other words, the fault tolerance is the ability of the network itself to maintain its functionality to an acceptable level even with the presence of interruptions caused by the failures of SNs. Astringent environments in which WSNs are deployed are the primary cause of failure of some components of the SNs and sometimes even of the whole network [1,2]. Therefore, the sensor field (deployment environment) and its characteristics may lead to provide some alternate technique to sort out the issues and help the WSN to provide service to an accepted level, even though the occurred fault is present in system. Since all the factors (Harsh environmental conditions, battery life, interrupts caused by humans) are not, easily determinable [3, 4] , so WSN should have a robust fault tolerant mechanism in order to deal with every possible failure and provide best sensor readings possible to end user as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1 WSN showing Sink as Gateway & Connected EU

Fault-tolerance is important for many WSN applications as they operate in capricious environment and should remain operational even if some failures occur. Dropped packets due to wireless interference, overload, node/link failures, and disconnected networks cause WSN failures. To be able to maintain efficient operations, WSNs must be designed to be resilient to these network dynamics. The extreme case would be during emergency response. WSN motes may fail or be blocked due to power failure and hardware/physical damage, or environmental interference. The failure of sensor mote should not affect the overall operation of the sensor network, is called Reliability or Fault tolerance, i.e., ability to provide sensor network functionality without any interruption

II. COMPARITIVE ANALYSIS OF FAULT TOLERANT AND RELIABILITY IMPROVEMENT PROTOCOLS

Detailed comparative analysis of reliability and fault tolerant techniques is shown in Table 1. E²SRT [5] protocol provides reliability since reliability of event detected is dependent on the sink node, which is aggregated from the reports of several source nodes, protocol provides desired reliability level with energy conservation.

GARUDA protocol [6] gives assurance for reliable data delivery in point to multipoint fashion from a sink node to various SNs. It is considered as reliable protocol for message delivery of small size messages, also supports a bi-stage negative acknowledgment (also known as NACK scheme) based process for recovery.

RCRT stands for Rate-Controlled Reliable Transport [7] it's having four major components, which are for congestion detection in the network, adaptation in transmission rate, allocation of transmission rate and for end-to-end retransmission. RCRT also implements a NACK scheme for recovery in case of an end to end the loss of data.

ZigBee Acknowledgement based Reliable Broadcast (ZARB) [8] protocol uses the acknowledgment mechanism for multicast and broadcast transmission for reliable transmission it smartly manages the broadcasted acknowledgments.

HERO [9] is a routing protocol and make uses of hierarchical structural design by allowing an effective, robust and multi-

hop communication in both directions among nodes, which are arranged in multiple tiers, to give developers the advantage to organize a Wireless Sensor Ad-hoc Network with as many tiers as needed.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF RELIABILITY AND FAULT TOLERANCE TECHNIQUES

Protocol	Enhanced Reliability	Constraint Satisfaction	Performance Improvement	Technique used
E ² SRT	Event to Sink Reliability	Dynamic topology, unreliable link	Energy Efficiency	Congestion control and reducing convergence time
GARUDA	Multiple reliability semantics	Packet size retransmission overhead	Latency, Energy efficiency	Loss recovery through minimum recovery set
RCRT	End to end Reliability	Asymmetric link hardware constraint	Network efficiency and flexibility	Implementation of NACK based end to end loss recovery scheme
ZARB	Packet reliability	More broadcast coverage time	Network efficiency	Active and passive ACK packet broadcasting
HERO	Bidirectional packet delivery	Node and Network constraint	Energy efficiency and life time	Efficient clustering technique
Data fusion with desired reliability	Transmission and information reliability	Unreliable data fusion structure	Energy Efficiency	Fusion depends on amount of information weight
Improved CICADA	End-to-End reliability	Mobility	Throughput reduced, retransmission delay, energy efficiency	Randomization and overhearing
Simple CRT based packet forwarding	Packet forwarding	Unreliable channels, dynamic topology changes and MAC Overhead	Power saving simplicity and fair distribution of energy consumption	Packet-splitting algorithm based on Chinese reminder theorem(CRT)
EIRDA	Clustering	Security	Energy Efficiency, lifetime and fault tolerance	Functional reputation for sensing aggregation and routing implemented
CAP	Event reporting	Node Constraint	Fault tolerance	Collaborative aggregation
Collaborative distributed detection	information reliability	Faulty nodes	Energy Efficiency, lifetime and fault tolerance	Coefficient of a regression polynomial, aggregation the median information and judges the final state of the event region

III. WSN NETWORK RELIABILITY AND FAULT TOLERANCE MODELLING

WSN Motes can communicate with each other by using the Radio Transceiver. Sensors are deployed in harsh environments. The possible way of sensors being any one of the two states: faulty and fault-free. When the sensor is in unsafe and safe is called as the most faulty and faultless respectively and it would be meaningless to transmit the faulty data to the cluster head from the sensors. Hence, it consumes more energy. If the WSN network fails to find the faulty sensor mote, then it is very difficult to control the amount of faulty data transmission. Moreover, it increases the transmission overhead. In the second state, if the characteristics of the sensors are good (i.e. the sensor then safe) directly aggregates the collected information. Update the

fault diagnosis protocol to improve the performance of accuracy.

Poisson distribution models reliability (Fault Tolerance) of a sensor node,

$$R_k(t) = \exp(-\lambda_k t)$$

to capture the probability of not having a failure within the time interval (0,t) with lambda is the failure rate of the sensor node k and t is the time period [10].

Example

Suppose: $\lambda = 3.5 * 10^{-3}$

t=10sec → R = 0.97
 t=20sec → R = 0.93
 t=30sec → R = 0.9
 t=50sec → R = 0.84

Whereas Reliability (Fault Tolerance) of a broadcast range with N sensor nodes is calculated from:

$$R(t) = 1 - \prod_{k=1}^N [1 - R_k(t)]$$

Overall there is need is to design the Protocols and algorithms to address the level of fault tolerance required by sensor networks. If the environment has little or very less interference, then the requirements can be more relaxed.

Example

How many sensor nodes are needed within a broadcast radius (range) to have 99% fault tolerated network? Assuming all sensors within the radio range have same reliability, prev. equation becomes

$$R(t) = 1 - [1 - R(t)]^N$$

Drop t and substitute f = (1 - R).
 0.99 = 1 - f^N → N = 2

i.e. Protocols and algorithms may be designed to address the level of fault tolerance required by sensor networks, and if the environment has little interference, then the requirements can be more relaxed.

Examples:

- House** to keep track of humidity and temperature levels → the sensors cannot be damaged easily or interfered by environments → low fault tolerance (reliability) requirement.
- Battlefield** for surveillance the sensed data are critical and sensors can be destroyed by enemies' → high fault tolerance (reliability) requirement.

i.e. Fault Tolerance (Reliability) is fully dependent on type of applications.

IV. STAGES OF FAULT DETECTION AND DIAGNOSIS

The stages involved in rule generation and fault-diagnosis is shown in the Fig. 2. Since fault-tolerant data aggregation, protocol is used for detecting and eliminating the faults will discard the faulty data from further proceedings.

Fig. 2 Phases of rule generation & Error Detection in WSN

Cluster head (CH) is responsible for aggregating the received information from sensor nodes. Aggregated data from CH is sent to sink node. Nodes use local sensitivity hashing scheme, which is the signature or thumb impression or compact representation of data for encoding. With sensor information locality sensitivity, hashing code is sent to the aggregation unit. Aggregation compares the similarity between the LSH and accordingly discards duplicate data based on codes, lead to improve bandwidth utilization and energy efficiency. Preliminaries in the aggregation network as in [11-12]. Similarity, distance metrics and local sensitivity hashing. Calculate the similarity between the data sets. Euclidean distance is the measure of distance between the pair of nodes. The cosine similarity of fault tolerant aggregation is given by following equation

$$\cos(\theta (V_i, V_j)) = \frac{V_i \cdot V_j}{(|v_i| |v_j|)} \quad (1)$$

Hash function (H) for any two point's p, q ∈ Rd as in [10]. It must satisfy the hashing function.

$$Pr[hr(u)] = hr(v) = 1 - \frac{\theta(u,v)}{\pi} \quad (2)$$

The hamming distance calculated as

$$b * (1 - Pr) = D_n(LSH_u, LSH_v) \quad (3)$$

The fault-tolerant scheme uses the LSH coding techniques and it increases the network lifetime of the network The hash function hour is defined as,

$$hr(u) = 1, \text{ if } r * u > 0 \text{ and } hr(v) = 0, \text{ if } r * u < 0 \quad (4)$$

Rough set concept has been explained in many applications of pattern recognition. An important aspect of the rough set concept is that decision making rules based on the measured sensor values. Rough set is a formal approximation of crisp set. Lower approximation of rough set classified as a member x.

$$\underline{B}(x) = U \{E_i \in U^B : E_i \in Cx\} \quad (5)$$

Upper approximation rough set classified as member 'x'

$$\overline{B}(x) = U \{E \in U^B : E \cap Cx \neq \emptyset\} \quad (6)$$

Fault class is defined as the difference between the upper approximation and lower approximation. The basic aggregation scheme computes the variance and standard deviation. Every aggregator performs the summing operation sum(S),

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \quad (7)$$

Sum of the squares as in equation (1)

$$V = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2 \quad (8)$$

IV. FAULT TOLERANCE AGGREGATION SCHEME FOR ERROR CORRECTION

While data collection, every sensor mote senses the environment k times and store the values in terms of the temperature, pressure, voltage, current, power and so on as per the sensor element attached. Let us consider the sensed values are n bits and now sensor node data vector size (k*n) bits. Nodes transmit the (k*n) bit data to the aggregate. As result, the energy level of battery is depleted. The sensor motes generates sensitivity hashing code (SCH) and reduces the data bits to be transmitted.

Major benefits of the sensitivity hashing code is, sensed data is represented in very less number of bits. Sensitivity hashing code applied to each sensor and obtain b bit sensitivity hashing code, but the value of b is less than (k*n). 'B' bit code sends to the cluster- head for aggregation.

FAULT IDENTIFICATION

For aggregation, the aggregator requests a sensor to transmit the sensitivity hashing code for processing. Based on request aggregator receives the sensitivity hashing code, and does the comparison of pair of sensor nodes. There are two major strategies to follow before aggregation. In the first case, the similarity between the pair of nodes discovered from the sensitivity hashing code and similarity threshold. Sometimes the sensitivity hashing code will not match each other because of the event affected by the adversary and local outlier. Data aggregator shares the adversary list among the neighbouring cluster to prevent the increment of count value of truthful data. Each cluster compares the hashing code with neighboring cluster and updates the count value. Moreover, Cluster exchange count list of local outlets.

In the second case, identical sensitivity hashing codes (SCH) found during the comparison or aggregation by CH then counter is incremented by one. CH (Cluster head) is capable of finding the sensor generating same SCH or code. Later on, the aggregation sends aggregated information to the base station. The role or responsibility of aggregation is to the remove redundant data received from the nodes. Using Rough set theory, i.e. when more than one sensor having the same code, the data aggregation considers only one data among the sensor nodes and forwards it towards sink, it reduces the amount of transmission.

PSEUDO CODE FOR FAULTY DATA ELIMINATION :

1. //Collect information and generate SHC//
2. **For loop**
3. Invoke Cluster-head session **do**
4. Poll or query for data from set of sensor E.
5. Process and generate sensitive code hash for data set.
6. **end for**
7. // Faulty/Redundant data Detection and Correction //
8. **For loop**
9. cluster-head session **do**
10. Send ACK to sensor for data received.
11. Compare the SHC for similarities.
12. Identify SHC, the code that is perfectly matching.
13. Detect & eliminate the faulty data (Redundant data).
14. **end for**
15. // Aggregation of received data //
16. **For loop**
17. cluster-head session **do**
18. Remove the faulty data.
19. Identify the sensor mote with same value.
20. Rough Set theory sends data from same value.
21. Aggregate the received data.
22. Forward the aggregated data towards base station.
23. **end for**.

V. REDUNDANT DATA ELIMINATION & CORRECTION SCHEME

During normal operation of wireless sensor networks, probable chance of failure occurrence is more. When sensor nodes become faulty or not behaving as per expectation it will not be identified, even though incorrect and faulty data is transmitted to the aggregation that leads to increase the transmission overhead and energy in the network as shown in Fig. 3(a).

Fig. 3 (a) Normal Case of Functional Sensor Network

As we know, incorrect and faulty data consume a certain amount of energy, although incorrect data is not sent to sink or mobile station. Sensor nodes with more than one similar data set, rough set theory will take only one set among the similar data set shown in Fig. 3(b). It does not send incorrect data to sink. Therefore, that transmission overhead is reduced and longevity increased.

Fig. 3(b) Sensor Network with fault elimination

Transmission paths for data is shown sensor networks, Sink node request to the cluster head of respective region for providing data or information. Once the request is made depending upon the sensor location, cluster head forward data towards base station. In case sensor or node is not located in the respective region then the node is transferred to next cluster head. If the node identified is present in the region of location, it sends a data to the base sink node. Later sink forms a selection path in order to send the data. Cluster head

network, makes use of two acknowledgments one for the sensor node to the cluster head and another from aggregator to the sink.

Aggregation algorithm tree construction of wireless sensor networks, as in [13]. Sensor nodes broadcast message from the leaf node to the parent node to all nodes receive the message. Aggregation operation is performed by the network on parent and its sub-node. However, aggregation is carried out in the tree at various levels such as intermediate node, leaf node and on leader node. Mobile station decodes the aggregated data and save it in the respective formats. After receiving the messages base station, verify the authenticity of received data to ensure security. The cluster head has the count of correct and incorrect data. Correct data should send to cluster head for aggregation. In addition, the rest of incorrect count eliminated. Finally, the data aggregation process ensures that no redundant data transmission and no compromised node transmitted from the sensors. Sink receives the aggregated data without any fault i.e. fault tolerant aggregation scheme is less complex and gives better performance

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS

Sensors are randomly distributed in terrain to measure the outer environment. The data aggregation scheme is simulated using the Network Simulator-2 [14], Fig. 4 shows the simulation environment. Data set size of sensor is $k=16$ and data set of similarity code $b=16$ bits. The data size can be varied from different sizes 4, 8, 16, 24 and 32 bits. To carry out the operation 32-bit data transmitted.

Fig. 4 Total Data transmission aggregator to the sink

Aggregation accuracy is measured based on the outcome of the error in the cluster head. The error is eliminated in the cluster head one and only if the difference between the aggregated data computed by the CH and data sent by the sensor without fault. The result is presented and compared with the neural network. Consequently, BER (Bit Error Rate) is reduced with increasing faulty sensor. Fault tolerant aggregation scheme successfully detect adversary and outlier with high precision. Aggregator eliminates all outliers in the network. Data aggregator does not receive faulty data result in accurate aggregation. Assume that network has 50 sensors in the network, which is randomly distributed in the environment. All the sensors try to send the data to the cluster-head, and use some amount of power and graph is plotted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Coverage of fault vs BER of proposed & ANN

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper addresses the issues specific to detection and elimination of the faulty node in wireless sensor network by using clustered architecture. Once the sensed data is classified in correct and incorrect data it would discard incorrect data and correct data is aggregated and forwarded to base station by the cluster head (CH). As a result, redundant data is eliminated; it helps in improving data aggregation accuracy, longevity and reduces data transfer overhead in wireless sensor networks.

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